

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Nebivolol HCl and Indapamide in Tablet

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 23 Sept. 2025

Keywords:

RP-HPLC, Nebivolol hydrochloride, Indapamide, UV, simultaneous estimation

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.17181590

ABSTRACT

The objective of the current study was to develop a simple, accurate, precise and rapid reversed phase high performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) method with subsequent validation using ICH suggested approach for the determination of Nebivolol hydrochloride (NEBI) and Indapamide (INDA) in tablets. The proposed RP-HPLC method utilizes a C18, 5 μ m, 250mm \times 4.6mm i.e. column in isocratic mode, mobile phase consisting of 0.074 M potassium dihydrogen phosphate and acetonitrile in the proportion of 40:60 (v/v) with 2% triethylamine and an apparent pH adjusted to 3.0 \pm 0.1 using orthophosphoric acid. The column effluents were subjected to UV detection at 282 nm. The retention times were 3.403 min and 7.907min for NEBI and INDA respectively at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. The linearity of the proposed method was investigated in the range of 50-150 μ g/ml ($r = 0.998$) for NEB and 15-45 μ g/ml ($r = 0.998$) for INDA respectively. The percentage mean recovery was found to be 98.01 for NEBI and 97.93 for INDA. Also, the method was statistically validated as per ICH guideline.

INTRODUCTION

Indapamide (INDA), chemically is a 4-chloro-N-(2-methyl-2, 3-dihydroindol-1-yl)-3-sulfamoyl-benzamide used as an antihypertensive agent and as a diuretic, which inhibits the reabsorption of sodium and calcium at the beginning of distal convoluted tubules. Nebivolol hydrochloride, chemically is a α , α' -(Imino bis (methylene)) bis (6-fluoro-3, 4 dihydro-2-H-1-benzopyran-2-

methanol) is an antihypertensive agent and α -adrenergic receptor blocker [1-3]. It produces sympatholytic effect on heart. Deep literature survey reveals that, HPLC [4-6], Spectrophotometric [7] method are reported for the estimation of INDA alone and combination with others. Spectrophotometric [8], HPLC [9-10], HPTLC [11] are reported for the estimation of NEBI. Simultaneous equation method and Q

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

absorbance ratio method was found for Nebivolol HCl and Indapamide in combine dosage form [12]. RP-HPLC method was not found so in present study, simple, accurate, precise, rapid RP-HPLC method is developed for the simultaneous estimation of these two drugs in combined dosage form.

Objective:

- By literature survey it was found that there is no official method is available for Nebivolol HCl and Indapamide in combination. Reported methods (Simultaneous equation method and Q absorbance ratio method) are available for Nebivolol HCl and Indapamide in combination.
- By literature survey RPHPLC method was not found for combination of Nebivolol HCl and Indapamide so, there is a thought of interest to develop new RP-HPLC method for estimation of Nebivolol HCl and Indapamide.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Instruments:

A Shimadzu RP-HPLC instrument (LC-20AT) equipped with an SPD-ZDA UV-Visible detector, manual injector with 20 μ L loop, and C18 column (250 mm \times 4.6 mm id, 5 μ m particle size) and Sprinchrom software were used. Sartorius CP224S analytical balance, ultra sonic cleaner and pH meter were used during the study.

Materials: Nebivolol HCl and Indapamide were received as a gift sample from Vaibhav Laboratory, Ahmedabad. Acetonitrile of HPLC grade and orthophosphoric acid of HPLC grade were purchased from S.D fine chemicals Ltd. Mumbai. The water for RPHPLC was prepared by triple glass distillation and filtered through a nylon 0.45 μ m –47 mm membrane filter (Gelman

Laboratory, Mumbai,India). Pharmaceutical formulation of NEBI and INDA were purchased from local pharmacy.

Chromatographic conditions: The column used for chromatographic separations was C18 (250 mm \times 4.6 mm i.d., 5 μ m particle size). The analytical wavelength was set at 282 nm and samples 20 μ l were injected. The chromatographic separations were accomplished using mobile phase comprised of 0.074 M potassium dihydrogen phosphate and acetonitrile in the proportion of 40:60 (v/v) with 2ml triethaylamine and an apparent pH adjusted to 3.0 \pm 0.1 using orthophosphoric acid, filtered through 0.45 μ m filter (Millipore) and deaerated in ultrasonic bath. Mobile phase was pumped at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min at ambient temperature.

Preparation of standard stalk solution:

For HPLC analysis 50 mg of Nebivolol HCl and 15 mg of Indapamide powder was weighed accurately using sartorius precision balance (readability 0.01 mg) and transferred in to 50 ml volumetric flask, dissolved and diluted to 50 ml with mobile phase.

Preparation of working standard solution:

From the standard stalk solution take 0.5, 0.75, 1, 1.25, 1.5 ml and transferred to separate 10 ml volumetric flask made up to mark with mobile phase for Nebivolol HCl and Indapamide.

Preparation of sample solution:

Twenty tablets were weighed accurately. Powder equivalent to 50 mg of Nebivolol HCl and 15 mg of Indapamide was weighed and transferred in a 50 ml volumetric flask and mobile phase was added. This solution was sonicated for 15 minutes and final volume was made to the mark with mobile phase. The solution was filtered through Whatman

filter paper No. 41. The filtrate (5ml) was transferred in a 50 ml volumetric flask and diluted to the mark with mobile phase to obtain sample solution.

Method Validation:

The method was validated for various parameters as per ICH guidelines.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Table 1: Regression characteristics and validation parameters

Parameters	NEBI	INDA
Calibration range	50-150 µg/ml	15- 45 µg/ml
Detection limit	0.670 µg/ml	0.365 µg/ml
Quantitation limit	2.032 µg/ml	1.108 µg/ml
Slope	8.674	16.31
Intercept	104.0	26.66
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.998	0.998
Intraday (%RSD)	0.291 – 1.093	0.634 – 1.411
Interday (%RSD)	0.390 - 1.254	0.428 – 1.447

Table 2: Data of recovery study

Drug	Amount added (µg/ml)	Amount added (µg/ml)	Amount found (µg/ml)	% Recovery ± S.D (n=5)
NEBI	1	4	4.8940	97.3522 ± 0.8885
	1	5	5.9208	98.41656 ± 0.5656
	1	6	6.1667	98.2884 ± 0.6948
INDA	1	1.2	2.1667	97.2282 ± 0.8805
	1	1.5	2.4751	98.3453 ± 0.5655
	1	1.8	2.7682	98.2340 ± 0.6957

Table 3: Parameters of chromatogram

System Suitability Parameters	NEBI	INDA
Retention Time	3.403	7.907
Tailing factor	1.4	1.525
Theoretical plate	6867	7156

Table 4: Estimation of NEBI and INDA tablets

NEBI			INDA		
Amount labeled (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Amount Found ± S.D. (n=5)	Amount labeled (mg)	Amount found (mg)	% Amount Found ± S.D. (n=5)
5	5.029	100.59 ± 0.605	1.5	1.51	100.714 ± 0.5361

Linearity for NEBI and INDA were found to be in the range of 50-150 µg/ml and 15-45 µg/ml respectively. Upon estimation in the tablet dosage form, label claim for both the drug was found to be in the limits. As evident from the values mentioned

in the table, lower values of LOD & LOQ indicate good sensitivity of the method. Interday & Intraday precisions were performed and %RSD values were found to be < 2%. The method showed

that there is no interference of the excipients on the analysis of pure drugs in marketed formulation.

CONCLUSION

Results are in good agreement with claim which indicates there is no interference of routinely used excipients. The proposed method was accurate, precise, simple, sensitive and rapid. The proposed method can be used for routine analysis of Nebivolol HCl and Indapamide in tablets.

Figure 1 HPLC Chromatogram of NEBI (100 µg/ml) and INDA (30 µg/ml)

Figure 2: Calibration curve of Nebivolol HCl

Figure 3: Calibration curve of Indapamide

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HOW TO CITE: Jaimin Prajapati*, Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Nebivolol HCl and Indapamide in Tablet, Int. J. of Pharm. Sci., 2025, Vol 3, Issue 9, 2563-2567 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17181590>

